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Professional training of police officers under conditions of contemporary challenges

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***Abstract:** The article is devoted to the actual issue of police education and training that is the foundation of an effective domestic security and safety system. Since crime has become more complex, threats have increased, and policing also involves constant community interaction, the role and training of police in democratic societies have been significantly important. **The purpose** is to analyze the*

*contemporary trends and challenges of police service and connecting with them changes and peculiarities of police training; to summarize the main principles, the most effective educational methods and training technologies of police training under the current conditions; to analyze knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary to police for successful police-public interactions. **Methods.** The study has used the methods of comparative and deferential analysis of contemporary state of police education and training, generalization of the base training principles, the theoretical analysis of the literary sources and the study of experience of practical realization of the researched issue. **Results.** Proper police training is crucial for ensuring that officers understand their role in law society, effectively resolve social conflicts and extreme situations, and maintain public trust. New and more complex challenges the police face (contemporary strategies for crime combating and prevention, new advanced technologies and equipment, etc.) affect the key principles of police training, namely: adherence to high professional standards, responsibility, honesty and impartiality, ethical and minimal use-of-force and others. Effective training methods and strategies, such as problem-based and practical-oriented ones, systematic and experiential approaches, realistic simulations and real-life scenarios, adaptability methodology allow forming decision-making skills, creative thinking, and interpersonal communication skills of police officers. **Conclusions.** Highly educated and quality trained police officers are able to solve problems effectively and make decisions, think creatively and interact with the public, reveal respect and impartiality, in addition to traditional tactical- combat skills, strict discipline, etc. Police training and activities based on respect for human rights, legal knowledge and justice, methods of conflicts de-escalation and the reasonable use-of-force policies are also of crucial importance. The new Ukrainian police established in 2014 are going currently through a difficult but important stage of reforms and formation using the best international experience.*

Key words: education of police officers, principles of training, challenges for police service, training methods and technologies, the National Police of Ukraine.

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***Анотація:** Стаття присвячена актуальному питанню освіти та підготовки поліцейських, що є основою ефективної системи внутрішньої безпеки та захисту. Оскільки боротьба зі злочинністю стала складнішою, загрози зростають, а також поліцейська діяльність передбачає постійну взаємодію з громадянськістю, роль і підготовка поліції в демократичних суспільствах набула важливого значення. **Метою** є аналіз сучасних тенденцій та викликів поліцейської служби та відповідної потреби суттєвих змін у підготовці поліцейських; узагальнення основних принципів, а також*

ефективних навчальних методів та технологій підготовки поліцейських у сучасних умовах; дослідження знань, навичок та вмінь, необхідних правоохоронцям для успішної комунікації з громадськістю. **Методи.** Використовувалися методи порівняльного та диференційного аналізу сучасного стану навчання та підготовки поліцейських, методи узагальнення базових принципів навчання, теоретичного аналізу літературних джерел та вивчення досвіду практичної реалізації досліджуваної проблеми. **Результати.** Належна підготовка поліцейських є вирішальним фактором для забезпечення розуміння офіцерами своєї ролі у правовій державі, ефективного вирішення суспільних конфліктів та екстремальних ситуацій, підтримки громадської довіри. Нові, складніші виклики, що стоять перед поліцією (сучасні стратегії боротьби зі злочинністю та її попередження, новітня техніка та оснащення тощо), впливають на ключові принципи підготовки поліцейських, а саме: дотримання високих професійних стандартів, відповідальність і неупередженість, етичне і мінімальне застосування сили, дотримання прав людей. Ефективні методи і стратегії навчання, такі як практико- і проблемно-орієнтоване навчання, системний і досвідний підхід, методи реалістичних симуляцій і ситуацій, адаптацій, – дозволяють сформувати у правоохоронців навички рішення проблем, критичного мислення, міжособистісної комунікації, стресостійкості. **Висновки.** Високоосвічені та якісно підготовлені поліцейські здатні ефективно вирішувати складні ситуації та приймати рішення, творчо мислити, взаємодіяти з громадськістю, проявляти повагу і неупередженість, крім володіння традиційними тактично-бойовими навичками, суворій дисципліни тощо. Підготовка і діяльність поліції, що базуються на дотриманні прав людини, правових знаннях і справедливості, методах деескалації конфліктів і розумного використання сили, також мають вирішальне значення. Нова Українська поліція, створена у 2014 році, нині

проходить нелегкий, але важливий етап реформування і становлення з використанням найкращого світового досвіду.

***Ключові слова:** навчання поліцейських, принципи навчання, сучасні виклики поліцейської служби, методи та технології навчання, Національна поліція України.*

Problem statement. Police education and training is the foundation of an effective domestic security and safety system. Crime has become more complex and threats have been increasing. Officers charged with enforcing laws must be open to new challenges and approaches. Since policing also involves the community interaction, the role of police in democratic societies has been increasingly important. Working closely and forming relationships with citizens from various backgrounds and ethnicities requires a socially intelligent and culturally aware police officer. Well-educated and trained officers are much more adept and used to solving problems, thinking creatively, and exhibiting open-mindedness. Efficient and professional distinction based on police education and training is particularly important for the transition countries like Ukraine, constructing new police forces, and undertaking reforms in the law enforcement sector.

While policing has changed dramatically in the last few decades, the way in which police recruits are trained has not fundamentally changed all that much. Police academies traditionally follow a paramilitary, boot camp-like model that emphasizes discipline, following orders, and a strict hierarchy. Discipline and following the command are certainly important and necessary aspects of police training and operations; however, the mission of a police academy is to prepare new police officers to serve and protect their communities with compassion and humanity. And officers need to develop skills beyond understanding the rules and following the orders of their superiors; they need to learn to think and act on their own. Police officers need communication skills, and they need to know how to be problem-

solvers and how to defuse tense situations. They also need to view the community as allies, not the enemy.

Literature Review. Since police training plays a crucial role in the development of officers, the issues of both police activities and police training have drawn attention of a number of domestic and foreign researchers and practical experts. Due to importance of the police functions to protect the rights and freedoms of the citizens, the society and the state, various aspects of police training have been examined. Thus, by L. Kleygrewe and R. Hutter, police training is a complex, multifaceted topic combining several educational components. Their study investigates training at six European law enforcement agencies and identifies challenges of current training organization and practice [1]. The authors Staller M., Koerner S. et al. debates about police professionalization and reform focusing on police education and training, observing and re-evaluating learning settings and goals of the complex system that has led to unfavorable outcomes in police - citizen encounters [2]. The study of V. Hutter, M. Kok and R. Oudeians is devoted to the didactical criteria for the high quality training of police officers, and also to the skills to be learned and applied in various situations like motor learning, performing under pressure, and motivation [3]. The researchers Bennell C., Jenkins B., Jones N. J. conducted a review to identify the knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for officers who police in democratic societies to successfully manage potentially volatile police-public interactions, they revealed and characterized 10 ones [4].

Additionally, the significant contribution of the Ukrainian scientists in the development of conditions, methodologies and techniques of police education should be noted. Thus, the Ukrainian researches Bondarenko V., Okhrimenko I., Prontenko K. and others have investigated the formation of significant professional skills and competencies of future police officers during studying at higher educational institutions and police academies [5]. The problems of improving policemen's professional psychological and behavioral skills, interpersonal communication skills

that are basis for the efficient official activities and aimed at de-escalating conflict situations, have been studied by Shvets D., Yevdokimova O., Barko V., Medvediev V., Fedorenko O., Radchenko K., Gorbenko D. et al. [6; 7; 8] The important issues of physical, tactical and firearms training for patrol policemen as the basis of their professional activities, and also innovative technologies for their studies are investigated in the works of Kazncheiev D., Volkov Yu., Myslyva O. etc. [9; 10]

Lopaeva E. and Boyko O. comparing police training system in Ukraine and foreign experience, confirm that officers training never ends due to reforms and innovations in legislation, therefore, every police officer should constantly improve their skills and knowledge, because the further professional path depends on it [11]. The specifics of the police officers training under conditions of the full-scale invasive war against Ukraine were analyzed by Ukrainian scientists L. Chystokletov, V. Polyvaniuk, D. Bodyriev and others who highlighted the theoretical and legal characteristics of the current police service, the main conditions of proper organization and police training in wartime, taking into account the specifics of combat operations and interaction with other military units, and improving preparation for actions in dangerous situations [12; 13].

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the overall problem.

Despite intensive researches on the different issues of police training, several essential aspects remain insufficiently researched. In particular, there is a lack of a comprehensive analysis of the contemporary trends and changes in policing and coming from those core principles and methodology of police training and education.

The examinations of police training practice – and, in particular, use-of-force training – for many years documented how both recruit and in-service training devoted considerable hours to firearms skills, defensive tactics, and other “hard” skills, but scant few hours to communications, de-escalation, crisis intervention, and other “soft” skills. When you consider the most important skill the police officers of the future should to have, it is communication – the ability to talk to people, not just

give them orders, but also to have confidence that they are effective communicators. In 2020, an independent research study in the USA found that if effective communication is a central element of training and key to successful de-escalation, that is associated with sizeable reductions in use-of-force incidents, and fewer injuries to both officers and citizens [14]. While there are pockets of innovation in policemen training, training as a whole has not kept pace with the dynamic changes taking place in policing. As a result, today's police officers are not universally being prepared for the challenges they face in providing police services in increasingly diverse and demanding communities. So, re-imagining policing begins with tackling how police officers are taught.

Therefore, **the article's goals** are to analyze the contemporary trends and challenges of police service and connecting with them changes and peculiarities of police training; and also to summarize the main principles of police training under the current conditions; to analyze the important knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary to police in democratic societies for successful police-public interactions; to disclose the most effective educational methods and training technologies including human rights-based police training and evidence-based approach.

Research Results. Effective professional police training helps ensure officers are professional in all aspects of their work. Proper training is crucial for ensuring officers understand their role in society, maintain public trust, and treat citizens with respect and fairness; and continued and advanced training improves the skills and qualifications of police officers throughout their careers. In the light of that, the recent research studies of the Police Executive Research Forum (USA) have concluded that globally policing changed dramatically over the past several decades in a number of important ways, namely:

- Crime-fighting according to the new strategies for controlling and preventing crime. These approaches (community policing, problem-oriented policing, intelligence-led policing, and others) are based on the principle of preventing crime

through partnerships with the community and other stakeholders, collaborative problem analysis and solving, effective use of technology and outside resources.

- Technologies, that is sophisticated records management and data analysis systems, powerful land mobile radio and mobile broadband networks, ballistics and other forensic applications, gunshot detection systems, and artificial intelligence and machine learning have all revolutionized how police respond to and solve crimes.

- Equipment. Police officers have access to new tools and equipment. More powerful and reliable service weapons, a wide range of less lethal tools, and technologies such as body-worn cameras and drones are helping today's officers be more efficient and effective.

- New challenges facing the police have grown more numerous and complex. Officers today are confronted by criminals armed with incredibly powerful firearms, "ghost guns" that can't be traced. They also face a new breed of offenders who understand how to use the Internet and the Dark Web to facilitate both traditional crimes such as drug and human trafficking as well as entirely new types of cybercrime. And while the police have traditionally confronted issues such as addiction, homelessness, and mental illness, the scope and complexity of these problems and their impact on the community are arguably unprecedented.[15; 16; 17]

All above mentioned nowadays changes influence the general process and key principles of police training that include: upholding professional standards, fostering public trust through community policing and procedural justice, and ensuring effective and ethical use of force. Effective training should also focus on legal knowledge, de-escalation techniques, and human rights; often using systematic methods like needs analysis and pilot testing [18].

As the latest researches state, a comprehensive policing transformation is based on *an evidence-based approach* to police training that emphasizes five principles, including that training should incorporate the following: 1) do no harm; 2) be based on policing activities, tactics, and strategies supported by evidence demonstrating

effectiveness in promoting the rule of law and protecting the population; 3) use educational training methods shown to be effective in transferring critical knowledge and skills to police; 4) be continuously evaluated; 5) be flexible and contextualized in its delivery [18, p.2].

So, coming from that the following foundational principles of police training can be distinguished:

- Ethics and accountability: Training emphasizes honesty, integrity, and accountability, often guided by codes of conduct and the seven principles of public life (selflessness, integrity, objectivity, accountability, openness, honesty, and leadership).

- Community and procedural justice: This involves training officers in community policing, active listening, treating citizens with dignity and respect, and understanding the role of history in building trust.

- Human rights: Training focuses on proactively respecting and protecting fundamental rights, ensuring actions like the use of force are based on principles of legality, necessity, and proportionality.

- Operational and tactical principles and use of force mean that when force is necessary, training emphasizes minimizing injury and damage, exercising restraint, and ensuring responses are proportionate to the situation.

- De-escalation and conflict resolution is that officers are trained in skills like de-escalation and active listening to resolve conflicts peacefully.

- Impartiality, that is training reinforces the principle of acting impartially and making decisions based on facts, not bias.

As police officers are frequently involved in potentially volatile interactions with the public, a primary goal in such interactions should always be to minimize the potential for harm, which will often involve the use of non-escalation and de-escalation strategies by officers. The study conducted by Bennell C., Jones N.J. et al. allowed identifying and confirming the importance of the knowledge, skills, and

abilities (KSAs) necessary for officers who police in democratic societies to successfully manage potentially volatile police-public interactions. They include: 1) knowledge of policies and laws; 2) an understanding of mental health-related issues; 3) an ability to interact effectively with, and show respect for, individuals from diverse community groups; 4) awareness and management of stress effects; 5) communication skills; 6) decision-making and problem-solving skills; 7) perceptual skills; 8) motor skills related to use-of-force; 9) emotion and behavior regulation; and 10) an ability to treat people in a procedurally just manner. The authors highlighted two additional critical KSAs: understanding the role of policing in a free and democratic society and tactical knowledge and skills [4]. So, to ensure that police-public interactions are managed effectively, police training may focus on the development and evaluation of the given knowledge, skills, and abilities.

However, as the experts confirm, overall, academies continue to train police officers to be warriors, even though their agencies and communities expect them also to be guardians, social workers, and community partners. So, there is a disconnect between the focus of the training that recruits receive and the range of skills that officers need to carry out the everyday demands of the job [14, p.8]. However, there is a range of other skills – communications, crisis intervention, community engagement, and problem-solving, for example – that officers will rely on day-in and day-out for the routine encounters that will occupy the vast majority of their time. Being a skilled communicator and problem-solver is crucial not only to addressing crime and disorder, but also to building community trust and support [14, p.21].

One of the core principles of police training according to current social demands is protecting human rights. *Human rights-based training* helps participants to proactively respect and secure fundamental rights. It ensures that the use of force is exercised in accordance with the principles of legality, necessity and proportionality that are crucial to the development of just societies. Such training will therefore enable police officers to fulfil the role envisaged for them in the area of justice,

freedom and security. By safeguarding all citizens' fundamental rights, police officers will engender trust throughout society, contributing to a virtuous circle that will encourage the reporting of crime, contribute to more effective crime fighting, enhance justice for victims and reduce societal tensions [19].

There are some crucial principles of human rights-based police training: a comprehensive and positive approach towards human rights; policing from a human rights perspective, the requirements both to protect and to respect; and a focus on the internalization of human rights. *The first principle* helps make clear that police are primarily a force designed to help realize human rights, which form the bedrock of any democratic and just society. Human, and fundamental, rights are also applicable to police officers and thus have an empowering effect. A crucial element and objective of a training course is, therefore, to overcome possible skepticism and create a positive approach towards human rights. *The second principle* reflects the fact that in many countries police have increasingly come to be seen as service providers to the public – as an organization which protects human rights. But police officers tread a narrow and difficult line each day between their dual obligations to protect and respect human rights, such as when they act to protect persons from torture or ill-treatment in cases of domestic violence. Police work to protect human rights must, for example, strictly apply proportionate means – especially when it comes to the use of force. This constitutes the biggest challenge in human rights-based policing: human rights protection with the least intrusive means. Fundamental rights cannot be reduced to legal standards alone. Though these standards are crucial, a broad understanding of human rights goes beyond the law. It also requires appropriate skills and attitude. It is of critical importance to see how a police officer interacts with society and what considerations and attitudes he or she uses to take decisions. *Internalising human rights* through education is a complex process with numerous facets, but one of crucial importance to the split second decisions police officers must often take [19].

Training not only needs to focus on effective policing approaches to promote the rule of law and protect the population. It also needs to use *effective educational methods and pedagogical techniques*. As police officers face more serious challenges in today's world, general training, including tactical training, which is traditionally present in academies, is no longer sufficient. Police officers need more than mechanical skills or the ability to memorize mechanically. Currently, according to researchers, higher-level training, which would include problem-based learning, the formation of critical thinking and interpersonal communication skills, is much more required [11].

The way police officers are trained may well matter as much as the content of skills and knowledge on which they are trained. Generally, effective training is developed through a systematic process that includes conducting a training needs analysis, developing training objectives, selecting methods of training, pilot testing the training design, and evaluating the outcomes of training [18, p. 3]. Improving the level of training can help to reduce public order violations and prepare police officers to interact with people of all segments of the population better. Training must help officers adapt to new technologies, strategies, and techniques for addressing crime.

Using advanced training methods and methodology are capable to enhance professional preparation of new officers and to solve the mentioned quests. Among distinguished by the experts ones, there are the following. There is a growing emphasis on training methods that develops critical thinking, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills, as opposed to just rote memorization. Practical training, especially using *realistic simulations* that mimic real conditions, is seen as a highly effective way to build skills. *Virtual reality* is being used to create immersive and realistic training environments, allowing officers to practice in high-stress situations with distracting elements. Effective training also involves a *systematic approach*, including needs analysis, setting objectives, selecting methods, pilot testing, and evaluating outcomes. Using *problem-oriented* and *experiential approaches* with

knowledgeable instructors can reinforce concepts through *real-life scenarios* and discussions. *Adaptability* is another methodology, that is training should avoid a one-size-fits-all assumption and be adapted to different conditions, such as urban versus rural settings. *Reinforcement* means that supervisors are often included in training to reinforce concepts and discuss real-life experiences [3; 11; 20].

Since the current state of recruit training demands remaking the system for how new police officers are trained, it is needed to adopt a new philosophy and culture around police training – one rooted in academic inquiry and developing recruits' critical-thinking and decision-making skills, as well as physical fitness and discipline. This new approach and culture are achieved through rigorous institutions of education that combine classroom instruction with small group exercises, realistic *scenario-based exercises*, and other approaches that follow the principles of adult learning. Because policing is, by its nature, a profession that involves dealing with stressful situations, recruits need to be challenged with stress-based training as well, largely through scenario-based exercises. Police academies should be places where expectations are high, and students are challenged to reach beyond the minimum standards of proficiency and demonstrate mastery of everything they are taught [14].

In 2014 Ukraine's law enforcement agencies faced the necessity of profound reformation due to the country's choice of integration with the EU and NATO as a priority of state policy and a direction for future development. One of the main challenges was to transform the corrupted militia into a modern police force. The foremost objectives of the reform were to achieve the highest standards in professional excellence, quality, responsiveness, as well as full respect of fundamental human rights, transparency, fairness, and competence. In 2015, the initial police reforms in Ukraine laid the foundation of the modern patrol police, and were a huge step forward in establishing a modern law enforcement system predicated on service for the citizens as well as serving and protecting. The level of trust in the police increased from 3% to 46% [21], and in November 2015, the

National Police of Ukraine and the Patrol Police Academy were established within the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

The essential part of the reforms has been the remodeling of the police education and training system. In particular, the qualification characteristics for the profession of police officer were approved jointly by the National Police of Ukraine and the Ministry of Internal Affairs. Subsequently, the development of the professional education standard (competencies of police officers) was launched. Most of the training programs for the National Police of Ukraine are elaborated by higher education institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the corresponding specialized police unit [21].

Conclusions. Strengthening the law enforcement to promote the rule of law and protect the population is particularly important as most nations currently face significant challenges in this field. Police training is the first and most significant step towards shaping more effective and professional policing. In the light of increasing demands to police activities, the issue of the high-quality training of police officers has become extremely important. The conclusion from the research conducted into the current state of recruit training and what should be done to improve training in the future is a vital evolution of training, focusing on new challenges and updated techniques. Since policing has changed considerably in recent decades, instead of traditional emphasis on strict discipline, following orders, tactical skills and a stress-based style of instruction, police officers need more communication and interpersonal skills, de-escalation and active listening skills to resolve conflicts and be problem-solvers, and community partners in their communities. Key areas of training should include crisis intervention, behavioral health, use-of-force policies, and developing critical thinking and decision-making skills through problem-based learning, and also human right-based approach, dealing with stressful situations and others.

Police training needs to use effective educational methods and practical techniques like realistic simulations and scenario-based exercises, problem-oriented

and experiential approaches etc. Under such conditions, the police officers as the most visible manifestation of government authority responsible for public security with front-line personnel in day-today contact with citizens, will treat citizens with respect and fairness and determine the positive public perception, maintain social safety and public trust.

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